

Review Paper on Properties of Black Cotton Soil using Marble Dust with Banana Fiber

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INTRODUCTION

Soil is the indispensable element of this nature. It is attached to everyone in one or another way. All the basic amenities of life, whether it is concerned with food, clothes and house, have been fulfilled by the soil. Without the soil it is just next to impossible to think about life on this earth. The word „soil“ is derived from the Latin word solium which according to Webster’s dictionary means the upper layer of the earth that may be dug or plowed; specifically, the loose surface material of earth in which plant grows. The term soil in soil engineering is defined as an unconsolidated material, composed of solid particles produced by disintegration of rocks. The voids space between particles may contain air, water or both. The solid particles may contain organic matter. The soil particles maybe separated by such mechanical means as agitation and water. Soil deposits in nature exist in an extremely erratic manner producing thereby an infinite variety of possible combination which will affect the strength of the soil and the procedures to make it purposeful. So is the particular case of black cotton soil with a wide range of challenges associated with the construction at sites with black cotton soil. In case of coarse grained soil, the mineralogical composition of the grain hardly affects the engineering properties of the soils perhaps the grain to grain friction is influenced. In such soils, inter particle forces other than those due to gravity are of no consequence, but the finer particles, the more significant becomes the forces associated with the surface area of the grains.

Literature Survey

Related to the topic of study review of literature was done. Considering the several researcher shows, our interest in RHA, SCBA, CHA, Fibers & FA few recent researches of various authors have been presented here.

- F.Saathoff, A.Gebissa et al (2019)** Various factors can affect the durability of roads, such as the strength of sub-grade, the quality of the sub-base and base course, the environments and properties of the soil used. Particularly, roads built on expansive soil are susceptible to early damage due to the swelling and shrinkage characteristics of this kind of soil under changing moisture conditions. The most common technique used to improve the properties of problematic soil is stabilization with additives.
- Khelifa Harichane et al (2019)** Chemical soil stabilisation has been practiced for a long time by adding different additives such as cement, lime and fly ash for improving their physico-mechanical properties. However, few studies related to the soil stabilisation using natural pozzolana (NP), lime (L) or the combination of both were recorded for different applications in civil engineering. An experimental investigation was undertaken to assess the effect of NP (containing 46.4% of silica) on the geotechnical properties of L-stabilised yellow clayey soil (YCS), which was obtained from Algerian East-West highway project. Both the L and NP were added to the YCS at levels of 0–8% and 0–20%, respectively.
- Bahar Demirel et al. (2018)** One of the most important parts of the mining industry is the marble industry. The use of marbles in the structures dates back to ancient times. However, especially in the last decades, the use of marble in the structures has increased too much. As the production in the marble factories increases, the amount of waste has reached a volume that cannot be stored. Marble wastes are formed as a result of cutting and polishing processes in marble factories. These by-products, which cannot be stored, should be utilized in other sectors. So, both economic losses can be reduced and environmental pollution can be prevented.
- S. P. Koganti et al (2018)** Expansive soil is a problematic soil due to its low strength and swell-shrink behavior. The expansive soils tend to swell and shrink with respect to increase and decrease of moisture content. Moreover, black cotton soil (expansive soil) is present in many parts of Krishna and Guntur districts of Andhra Pradesh in which state’s new capital "Amaravathi" was announced. So, it is necessary to find out cost effective materials for stabilization of black cotton soils which will save economy of the state while constructing flexible pavement.
- Akshaya Kumar al (2017)** Considerable rise in CBR value of soil with reinforcement of Jute fibre and this rise in CBR value will significantly reduce pavement subgrade thickness.

6. **Liet Chi Danget al (2017)** This investigation exhibits a series of laboratory tests conducted to evaluate the influences of bagasse fibres and hydrated lime addition on the engineering properties and shrink-swell behaviour of stabilised expansive soils. Bagasse fibre is industrial waste by-product left after the crushing of sugar cane for juice extraction that was used in this study as reinforcing component for expansive soil stabilization. The expansive soils used in this investigation were collected from Queensland, Australia. In order to investigate the influences of bagasse fibres on the engineering behaviour of expansive soil, varying proportions of randomly distributed bagasse fibres of 0.5%, 1.0%, and 2.0% were added to expansive soil and hydrated lime-expansive soils mixed with different bagasse fibre proportions were also investigated.
7. **Akshaya Kumar al (2017)** Considerable rise in CBR value of soil with reinforcement of Jute fibre and this rise in CBR value will significantly reduce pavement subgrade thickness.
8. **Amrutha Mathew et al (2016)** The expansion of sisal fiber, bagasse cinder and glass powder squander in different extents with dark cotton soil and mix on the above extent of fixings is examined. To accomplish this objective test thinks about were conveyed in two stage. In the primary stage, the physical properties of soil, for example, molecule measure dispersion, particular gravity, Atterberg's cutoff points, swelling weight were resolved. In second stage, different tests were performed on dark cotton soil utilizing distinctive extent of sisal fiber, bagasse fiery debris, glass powder squander and from the most extreme estimations of quality test a mix of 0.9% sisal fibre, 7% bagasse slag and 14% glass powder squander was likewise performed. The outcomes demonstrated that with expansion of sisal fiber, bagasse fiery remains and glass powder squander the dry thickness expanded and ideal dampness content was observed to diminish. The unconfined compressive quality and California bearing proportion esteems expanded with expansion of ideal level of sisal fiber, bagasse fiery debris and glass powder waste to the blend of dark cotton soil. The best outcome was gotten for blend of dark cotton soil and ideal dose of 0.9% of sisal fiber, 7% bagasse slag and 14% glass powder squander .
9. **Rohit et al (2016)** By and large, soils in characteristic state don't present satisfactory soil properties to be utilized as asphalt (street) benefit layers. Keeping in mind the end goal to change their geotechnical parameters to meet the necessities of specialized particulars of development industry; soil balanced out systems are typically accentuated. The goal of this work is to use the viability of Bagasse Ash (BA) material to improve the properties of regular soil (NS) utilized for materials in asphalt sub review. The exploratory work included list properties to arrange the dirt example. The preparatory examination of the common soil demonstrates that it is has a place with A-6 class in the AASHTO soil arrangement framework. Though according to IS arrangement this class are for the most part low compressibility mud soil (CL). Fluid farthest point, plastic breaking point, versatility file, OMC, MDD, swelling weight and CBR tests were utilized to assess properties of balanced out soil. The regular soil was settled with BA in ventured convergence of 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25% and 30% by dry weight of the dirt independently. All settled fake soil tests were additionally cured for 96 hours for CBR test in completely soaked condition. The test outcomes show that the expansion of BA improves the level of fractional size appropriation, however with expansion of BA till 20% the L.L, PL, PI and swelling weight diminishes, while these parameters additionally increments in this breaking point past i.e. 20% to 30% of BA, Specific Gravity and MDD diminish with expansion of BA, for all rate esteems, though ideal dampness content increments in every material. The CBR esteem increments with expansion of BA till 20%, the CBR esteem increments and it is diminishes with advance expansion of BA past 20% to 30% for both condition (doused and Unsoaked) gasse Ash (SCBA) from Sugar Industry can be utilized as Stabilizing Material for Natural Soils , International Journal for Scientific Research and Development
10. **Muthu Kumar M and Tamilarasan (2016)** Represents a study to 'Experimental Study on Expansive Soil with Marble Powder.' Soil stabilization is required when the soil available for construction is not suitable for the particular use of all the soils, Expansive soil causing major problems to the civil Engineering structures. Such soil are having high volume changes upon adding the water. Soil stabilization using chemical admixtures is the oldest and most widespread method of ground improvement. The conventional soil stabilization techniques are generally expensive, involving large quantities of costly materials. Due to shortage of energy, materials and also the high cost of construction operation, there is a need to go for alternate low cost materials. In this study, waste marble dust which is the by product of marble industry, is used for the soil stabilization. Disposal of this waste creates serious problems to the humans surrounding them as well as acts as a pollutant so affect the ecological system of the environment (Gupta et.al 2014). So that, we decided to use the marble powder is used to improve the Engineering property of expansive soil, thus making it more stable and also to stabilize the soil with a very low cost material. The marble powder has very high lime (CaO) content and is reported Many researchers. We have added the marble powder to the expansive soil as 5%, 10% 15%, 20%, 25% and studied the compaction characteristics and strength characteristics.
11. **Akshaya Kumar Sabat and Radhikesh P. Nanda (2015)** Represents a study to the effect of Marble dusts on strength and durability of an expansive soil stabilized with optimum percentage of Rice Husk ash (RHA). The optimum percentage of RHA was found out be 10% based on Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) tests. Marble dust was added to RHA stabilized expansive soil up to 30%, by dry weight of the soil, at an increment of 5%. Compaction tests, UCS tests, Soaked California Bearing Ratio (CBR) tests, Swelling pressure tests and Durability tests were conducted on these samples after 7 days of curing. The UCS, and Soaked CBR of RHastabilized expansive soil increased up to 20% addition of Marble dust. Further addition of Marble dust had negative effects on these properties. The Maximum Dry Density(MDD) and Swelling pressure of expansive

soil goes on decreasing and Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) goes on increasing irrespective of the percentage of addition of Marble dust to RHA stabilized expansive soil. From the Durability test results it was found that the addition of Marble dust had made the RHA stabilized expansive soil durable. For best stabilization affect the optimum proportion of Soil: Rice husk ash: Marble dust was found to be 70: 10: 20.

Problem identification

- Construction of highway involves huge outlay of investment. A precise engineering design may save considerable investment as well a reliable performance of the in-service highway can be achieved.

Objectives

The objectives of the research are outlined below:

- To study the variation of Grain size distribution, Liquid Limit, Plastic Limit, Plasticity Index, Specific Gravity, Optimum Moisture Content, Maximum Dry Density, Swelling Pressure and CBR for both conditions of natural soil.

CONCLUSION

The soaked CBR value of the raw soil and after mixing of Marble Dust with banana fiber in the soil, there is remarkable change in CBR value.

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